

A New Analysis for the Evaluation of the Second Order Interaction Rate Constant from Electro-Osmotic Pressure Data

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The second order interaction rate constant, L_{112} , occurring in electro-osmosis, has been evaluated in a number of ways¹. A new analysis has been attempted, in this present communication, to evaluate the same i.e L_{112} from the values of the steady state electro-osmotic pressure for the acetone/pyrex sinter system¹.

The phenomenological rate equation for the transport of matter in electro-osmosis is given by the expression¹⁻⁴

$$J = L_{11} (\Delta P/T) + L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{111}(\Delta P/T)^2 + L_{112} (\Delta P/T) (\Delta\phi/T) + L_{112}(\Delta\phi/T)^2 + \dots \quad (1)$$

where J denotes the transport of matter, ΔP and $\Delta\phi$ denote the pressure and potential differences respectively across the membrane, L_{ik} ($i, k=1, 2$) and L_{ijk} ($i, k, j = 1, 2$) are known as the rate constants. When $i \neq k$ and/or j L^s are described as interaction rate constants.

If the electro-osmotically transported matter is not allowed to flow out of the system, an electro-osmotic pressure is developed which causes the flow of matter in the reverse direction of electro-osmosis. In the steady state the flow in the opposite directions balances each other and the net flow across the membrane becomes zero i.e. $J=0$. Further in the range where solvodynamic and electro-osmotic flows are linearly related to ΔP and $\Delta\phi$ respectively, the terms with higher powers in ΔP and $\Delta\phi$ in equation (1) will vanish. Equation (1) is then written as

$$J = L_{11}(\Delta P/T) + L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{112}(\Delta P/T) (\Delta\phi/T) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

In the steady state, when $J=0$, equation (1) may be easily transformed to give

$$(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{J=0} = - (L_{11}/L_{12}) - (L_{112}/L_{12} \cdot T) \Delta\phi \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Accordingly if the values of $(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{J=0}$ at constant temperature is plotted against the applied potential difference, $\Delta\phi$, a straight line should be obtained. Its slope would thus give the information about the order and magnitude of L_{112} .

The values of $(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{J=0}$ have been obtained from the recent experimental data¹ on electro-osmotic pressure in acetone/pyrex sinter system at 30°. These are plotted against

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$\Delta\phi$ in the given figure. The electro-osmotic pressure has been indicated in the cm of acetone height which can be readily converted in dyne cm^{-2} by multiplying the height with ρ , the density of acetone⁵ at 30° , and g , the acceleration due to gravity.

FIG. 1

The straight line drawn through the points has the statistical sanction^{6,7}. The correlation factor⁷, is found to be 0.733. The theory of statistical probability⁸ indicates more than 99.5% linear relation between the points. The slope and the intercept of the line have been obtained by the method of least squares⁹. The values are $5.01 \times 10^{-6} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ and $10.34 \times 10^{-3} \text{ volt dyne}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$. The reported value of L_{12}/T for the system at 30° is $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1}$. Hence the order and the magnitude of L_{12} is found to be $11.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ oK}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with the values reported earlier¹.

It may be noted that according to equation (3) the value of the intercept is given by the quantity $-(L_{11}/L_{12})$. Its inverse value (L_{12}/L_{11}) is found to be $96.71 \text{ dyne cm}^{-2} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ which is in excellent agreement with the value of the intercept obtained by plotting $(\Delta P/\Delta\phi)_{j=0}$ against $(\Delta P)_{j=0}$. The intercept in the latter case is given by the quantity $-(L_{12}/L_{11})$ and its reported¹ value is $97.91 \text{ dyne cm}^{-2} \text{ volt}^{-1}$.

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